

Minutes of the 49th Experimenters' Meeting
The Cosener's House, Abingdon, Thursday 21st June 2012
(This document was finalised on 19th July 2012)

Present:

Dr Bogdan Antonescu⁶ (BA)
Mr Les Dean^{1,4} (LD)
Mr David Edwards³ (DE)
Dr Catherine Gaffard³ (CG)
Miss Gemma Holmes³ (GH)
Dr David Hooper^{4,5} (DAH) Secretary
Dr Chris Lee⁷ (CFL)
Dr Graham Parton^{2,5} (GAP)
Dr Jeremy Price³ (JP)
Prof Geraint Vaughan⁶ (GV) Chair

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⁵Rutherford Appleton Laboratory (RAL)

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Other abbreviations used in this document:

BL(WP) Boundary-Layer (Wind-Profiler)
DIAMET DIAbatic influences on Mesoscale structures in ExTropical storms
DPW Dave Wareing (University of Manchester technician)
DWD Deutscher Wetterdienst (German weather service)
EUCOS EUMETNET Composite Observing System
FGAM Facility for Ground based Atmospheric Measurements
GNSS Global Navigation Satellite System
GPS Global Positioning System
JJ Jon Jones (Met Office)
LEO Low Earth Orbit
MST(R)(F) Mesosphere-Stratosphere-Troposphere (Radar) (Facility)
NERC Natural Environment Research Council
NLC Noctilucent Cloud
PC Personal Computer
(P)MSE (Polar) Mesosphere Summer Echo
RMS Root Mean Square
TROSIAD TROopause folding, Stratospheric Intrusions And Deep convection
UPS Uninterruptable Power Supply
UT Universal Time

1. Minutes of the previous meeting

DAH pointed out that he has used the same number - 48.4.1 - for two new action items, on pages 6 and 7. The second one should have been numbered 48.4.2.

DAH had written, at the bottom of page 11, that just "3 lines of code" will need to be changed to allow the full altitude-resolution of wind-profiler (WP) data to be assimilated into the Met Office's model. CG clarified that it would take a bit more effort than that. Further details are given in the next section.

2. Matters arising

ACTION ITEM 46.4.1 DK to set up a working group for developing quality control algorithms for wind-profiling radars.

DISCONTINUED

GV pointed out that this was really an issue for DK (who had to cancel his attendance of this meeting at the last minute) and so should be discontinued as an action item for these meetings.

ACTION ITEM 46.5.3 GAP and DK to investigate the possibility of storing data from all of the Met Office's new Jenoptik Laser Cloud Base Recorder (LCBR) on the BADC.

ONGOING

GAP reported that there had been little progress on this over the last few months.

ACTION ITEM 47.2.1 DAH to modify the MST radar signal processing software, as soon as possible, to allow it to make use of updated Python programming libraries.

ONGOING

ACTION ITEM 47.2.2 DAH to ensure, as soon as possible, that MST radar data products generated by the latest version of the signal processing software are available for the entire observation archive.

ONGOING

DAH reported that he dedicated some time to the first of the above two items. He has almost completed changes to the routines required to read to and write from netCDF files. He will return to these tasks as soon as possible. GV emphasised how much better the version 3 data products were than their predecessors. Consequently it is scientifically important that the version 3 products are available for the entire observation archive.

ACTION ITEM 47.3.2 DAH to recreate cloud base altitude files, starting from 2nd November 2010, with the time stamps corrected.

ONGOING

This is a low priority task and so DAH has no plans to complete it in the near future.

ACTION ITEM 47.5.1 GAP to ensure that the BADC archive Met Office lightning data to cover the TROSIAD campaign period.

ONGOING

GAP reported that he had made data available to BA for the period of the TROSIAD campaign. However, he (GAP) needed to ensure that the data were in an appropriate format before they could be made generally available through the BADC archives.

ACTION ITEM 48.4.1 DAH and GAP to remove from public view on the BADC those surface wind files which are known to contain data of dubious quality.

COMPLETED

Details are given in section 3c.

ACTION ITEM 48.4.1 DAH and JDE to investigate the opportunities for returning the spare MST radar transmitter to working order.

ONGOING

Some progress has been made on this. Details are given in section 4g.

CG elaborated on how WP radar data are assimilated by the Met Office. The wind profiles are treated like those from radiosondes, i.e. with data only input at "significant levels", where there are relatively sharp changes of wind vector as a function of altitude. Model levels are then populated with values which are interpolated between those at the significant levels. Although this is appropriate for radiosonde data, it can cause problems for WP radar data owing to gaps in regions of low signal strength. Interpolated values are particularly inappropriate when the peak of the jet falls within a radar data gap. It's not clear whether AMDAR data from aircraft are treated in the same way. CG now has access to details of exactly what has been assimilated and so she will be able to investigate the issue further.

The urban scheme of the Met Office's model will be run at 200 m horizontal resolution. At such small scales it will be necessary to know exactly how WP observations are made. For example, some WPs within the inhomogeneous European network only observe for half the time during a 30 minute averaging period. Others observe for the whole time.

3. Facility Report - DAH

3a) Electricity

The Uninterruptable Power Supply (UPS) units indicated that brief electricity supply disruptions (i.e. with durations of no more than 1 s) occurred on 28th April, 19th May, and 11th June 2012. A disruption of 5 s occurred on 13th February 2012. None of these had any impact on the equipment powered by the UPS units.

3b) Telecommunications

On 3rd February 2012 DAH switched the NERC and Manchester broadband connections to a new package with Eclipse, the existing Internet Service Provider. The "*Business Bronze*" package has a monthly 50 GByte peak-time usage allowance for half of the cost of the earlier unlimited package. Typical monthly download volumes are just a few GByte. DAH also switched to Eclipse's "*TalkMore Business*" package, which gives 1000 free minutes of telephone calls per month to 01, 02 and 03 numbers. At present the line rental is still paid through BT, although further savings could be made by switching this to Eclipse also. Moreover, it is typically easy to speak to an advisor when calling Eclipse's helpline. When there had been an apparent line fault on 5th February 2012 (see below), DAH had found it virtually impossible to get an update by calling BT's helpline.

DAH suspects that the problem on 5th February 2012 (a Sunday) might have been a broadband issue rather than a line one. The NERC internet connection was lost at around 00:00 UT and was restored when Dave Wareing (DPW) power-cycled the modem the following (Monday) morning. The

33 hour backlog of wind-profile messages was sent to the Met Office as soon as the connection was re-established. A similar problem occurred at 06:20 UT on Sunday 19th February 2012. DPW power-cycled the modem on the following (Monday) morning. A third loss of internet, at 23:20 UT on Friday 16th March 2012, was spotted by DAH on the following day (he was in the office preparing for the MST13 workshop). DPW happened to need to go to site and power-cycled the modem the same afternoon. A fourth loss of internet occurred at 13:50 UT on Friday 30th March. LD was able to visit site and power-cycle the modem by 15:50 UT the same day. A fifth loss occurred at 01:00 UT on Sunday 27th May 2012. LD spotted this from home and visited the site the same day to power-cycle the modem at 17:00 UT. Eclipse confirmed that the loss of connection on 19th February was the result of an “administrative reset” at their end. Although the causes of the other losses are not known, DAH suspects that they also originated at Eclipse’s end.

JP reported that he had also had problems with broadband modems losing their internet connection. He had dealt with this by connecting the modems to timer switches. This ensured that they were power-cycled on a daily basis. He suspects that, in at least some instances, the internet problem might be solved simply by phoning the line to which the modem is connected.

DAH reported that it had not been possible to establish a dial-up connection with the surface wind data logger at Frongoch since 25th May 2012. LD discovered that the telephone at the Frongoch end did not have a dialling tone and so the problem was reported to BT. It appears that the problem is not a trivial one and a new supporting pole is required at some point along the line. GV suggested that it might be possible to use a mobile broadband connection instead. This had worked well for the mobile lidar when it was away on campaigns. DE added that the Met Office have started to use 3G connections for some remote applications.

3c) Data management

In connection with action item 48.4.1, Frongoch surface wind files for the following dates have been removed from public view on the BADC: 12th - 16th October 2011, inclusive, and 3rd - 5th January 2012, inclusive.

DAH warned that there will be some slight changes to MST radar data variable names when he begins to reprocess the entire archive, i.e. in connection with action item 47.2.2. Following a recommendation made by GAP, he will include the current (version 3.2) names as variable attributes in the new files. There will also be slight changes to the reported altitudes since he will adopt a more-precise value than 3.0×10^8 for the speed of light.

CFL asked whether DAH intended to include details of when individual transmitters had been out of action. This is relevant for turbulence studies, when the loss of one or more transmitters will alter the beam shape. DAH thought that such information should be included in supplementary files as, in general, these are only known after the event.

3d) Miscellaneous

The small huts which house the MST radar primary power splitters within the antenna array were replaced during March 2012. The original structures had been in place for over 20 years and were in a poor state of repair. They had proved to be difficult to access during the period of radar renovation in March 2011. Consequently the new huts were made slightly taller and with access hatches at either end. DAH was very impressed by David Yarwood, the local carpenter who had designed and installed the new units. His good time-keeping was particularly important as the Met Office needed to be warned of down-time in advance, i.e. for 8th, 9th, 13th, 14th, 15th and 16th March 2012. The final coat of waterproofing was not applied to the huts until 24th May, owing to the lack of dry days.

Richard Mayo, an engineer from the Australian company ATRAD that had carried out the MST radar

renovation in March 2011, revisited the site during the final week of March 2012. He had been in Germany to attend the MST13 workshop during the previous week. The radar was powered down for a few hours on 27th and 28th March 2012 to allow Richard to inspect a random selection of phasing units. All were found to be in a good condition after 1 year of continuous operations in the field.

Approximately 30 Environmental Science undergraduates from the University of Manchester visited the radar site on 11th April 2012. DAH talked to them about the MST radar whilst GV talked to them about the lidars. The students were given an exercise to take measurements from hand-held met sensors around the site. They later used these in an exercise to demonstrate measurement variability.

DAH showed surface met data from the site for 8th and 9th June 2012, when it had rained quasi-continuously for a period of 34 hours. The resultant flooding in the Aberystwyth area was widely reported in the media. LD and DPW had confirmed that, despite flooding nearby, the site had not been adversely affected. DAH was reassured to hear this since the site is within a designated flood risk area. It had been necessary to submit a "Flood Consequences Analysis" to the Environment Agency, in September 2006, in order to gain planning permission to build the large green shed. GV reported that the rain was associated with a quasi-stationary occluded front. A combination of moist air from the sea and the orography of mid-Wales had lead to an enhancement of rain at low levels through the seeder-feeder mechanism. CFL pointed out that the Met Office's rainfall radar network had not been effective at detecting this rain. GV attributed this to the shadowing effect of the hills. GV asked if DAH could provide the integrated rainfall for this event.

ACTION ITEM 49.3.1 DAH to provide GV with the integrated rainfall for the 8th - 9th June 2012 event.

NEW

DAH completed this action shortly after the meeting. As measured by the tipping bucket raingauge, 69.0 mm of rain fell between 23:00 UT on 7th June 2012 and 09:00 UT on the 9th. This had been preceded by 6.8 mm, on 7th June, spread over 3 separate rain events.

DPW had reported, on 15th June 2012, that stoats appear to have once again taken up residence in the attic of the bungalow. This had previously happened in July 2008, as reported in the minutes of the 41st meeting. On this occasion, DPW managed to film one of the stoats entering the bungalow through a cable conduit. LD and DPW suspect that the stoats are just using the bungalow whilst they raise their kits. DAH warned that no attempt should be made to block the conduit until it was certain that all of the stoats had moved out.

4. NERC Instrument Report - DAH

Full details of instrument performance issues can be found at http://mst.nerc.ac.uk/cgi-bin/mstlog_public/mst_event_search.py.

4a) Campbell Scientific surface met sensors

The tipping bucket raingauge failed to detect a moderate precipitation event, between 17:00 and 24:00 UT on 18th May 2012, which was seen by the WXT510. LD cleaned the instrument on 22nd May and found that it had been blocked by a grey crust.

4b) Campbell Scientific surface wind sensors

As reported in section 3b, it has not been possible to establish a dial-up connection with the Frongoch data logger since 25th May 2012.

4c) Vaisala WXT510 surface met and wind sensors

The precipitation sensor failed to detect 3 mild rain events, which were seen by the tipping bucket rain-gauge: 14:00 - 20:00 UT on 16th February 2012, 01:10 - 10:20 UT on 1st June 2012, and 06:00 - 10:10 UT on 3rd June 2012. It appears that, in each case, the rain was falling too gently to generate a significant piezo-electric signal. Rain events were subsequently detected without any intervention having to be taken.

There have been two gaps in data collection as a result of the acquisition PC ("augustus") being rebooted: 12:06 - 14:45 UT on 8th March 2012, and 09:55 - 12:56 UT on 15th March 2012.

4d) Vaisala LD40 laser ceilometer

There have been a few short gaps, i.e. of no more than a few minutes, when no data were captured: on 16th, 18th, and 19th February 2012. The cause for these is not known.

On the subject of the Met Office's intentions to locate a Jenoptik ceilometer at the radar site, DE reported that they have had problems procuring new instruments.

4e) Sky-camera

DAH will supervise a work experience student at RAL during the week of 9th - 13th July 2012. Five previous students have contributed to the log of interesting phenomena. It now spans almost the first year of operation, i.e. 25th April 2007 - 1st April 2008.

4f) NLC-camera

In support of his attempts to understand the mesosphere summer echoes (MSEs) seen by the MST radar (see section 6d), DAH installed a Noctilucent Cloud (NLC) camera at the Chilbolton Observatory on 7th June 2012. NLCs are composed of ice crystals, which form as a result of the extreme cold (< 150 K) of the mid and high latitude mesopause (i.e. at around 85 km) during the mid-summer months. Their visibility depends on them remaining sunlit after the lower atmosphere is in the Earth's shadow. Consequently they are preferentially seen between NW (dusk) and NE (dawn). The optimal viewing range is between latitudes of 55° and 57° N. However, they can be seen with diminishing frequency and elevation at lower latitudes. Unfortunately, the northward view from the MST Radar site (52.4° N) is blocked by the valley side. Consequently DAH opted to install the camera at Chilbolton (51.1° N), which has a low horizon in all directions.

The camera consists of a Canon EOS 550 body and a Tamron SP 17-50mm F2.8 Di II LD lens. The camera body was chosen because it can be triggered at set times (currently every 5 minutes between 20:30 and 03:30 UT) by *gphoto2* software on a Linux PC. The lens was chosen because it has a wide field of view (67° in the horizontal at 17 mm focal length) and a wide aperture. The latter is important for low-light conditions. Moreover, the Tamron lens is reputed to have very good image quality and costs half as much as the equivalent Canon lens.

The camera has been located within the Receive Cabin at the Big Dish end of Chilbolton's 500 m range. Fortuitously this points to within a few degrees (to the East) of North. Initially reflections of instrument lights from the inside of the cabin window obscured the images of the sky. However, this was resolved by placing the camera right against the window and within a light-shielding box. A more-fundamental limitation has been the prevalence of obscuring tropospheric cloud. Nevertheless, the camera has seen signs of what might be NLC during the evening of 13th June 2012 (clear and unambiguous NLCs were photographed a few days after the meeting - on the night of 24th/25th June 2012).

DAH proposed that he would make scaled-down versions (900 by 600 pixels) of all images available through the BADC. However, he will only keep the 18 Mpixel originals (5184 by 3456 pixels), which amount to approximately 330 MBytes per night at the current acquisition rate, for those nights when

something interesting can be seen. DAH expressed an interest in deploying additional NLC-camera systems if suitable sites could be found.

4g) MST Radar

DE presented a summary of the MST radar's performance over the past few months. The EUCOS statistics are derived from comparisons of measured winds against the Deutscher Wetterdienst (DWD) model fields. The monthly "Timeliness" and "Availability" values had almost always exceeded the EUCOS targets of 90% and 95%, respectively. "Availability" was slightly below target for February 2012, probably as a result of broadband problems, and for March 2012, when replacement of the primary power splitter huts (see section 3d) had led to some down time. The "Quality" values were also generally good and only occasionally exceeded the 5.0 m s^{-1} maximum target.

DE also presented statistics derived from comparisons made against the Met Office's UKV model, i.e. a local high-resolution version. For wind direction, there is no significant bias and the Root Mean Square (RMS) differences, 5° - 10° , are fairly low. Measured wind speeds show a slight negative bias, $\sim 1 \text{ m s}^{-1}$, at the higher levels. EUCOS statistics suggest a slightly larger bias. However, DE is not sure if EUCOS make comparisons against the global or a local version of the DWD model. A similar difference is seen for radiosonde data. DE is encouraged that RMS differences of the radar data against the UKV model are consistently low. Nevertheless, the occasional rogue data point does get incorrectly flagged as being reliable. These can have speeds and/or directions which are very different to those of their nearest neighbours. Despite the fact that these tend to be confined to just a few altitudes gate of a single 30 minute averaged profile, the magnitude of the errors can be so large that they affect the EUCOS "Quality" statistics for the whole day. The following examples were identified: 22:30 - 23:00 UT on 22nd May 2011 at 10.79 and 10.94 km, 06:00 - 06:30 UT on 29th May 2011 at 9.89 - 10.19 km, at 21:30 - 22:00 UT on 2nd September 2011 at 12.58 and 12.73 km, 15:00 - 15:30 UT on 4th December 2011 at 9.29 km, 09:00 - 09:30 UT on 4th February 2012 at 9.59 km.

DAH is mystified as to how such clearly-erroneous data could pass the quality control checks, which tend to be highly-effective at removing outlying data points. GV pointed out that DAH should investigate these issues before he starts reprocessing the entire observation archive.

ACTION ITEM 49.4.1 DAH to investigate, prior to carrying out action item 47.2.2, the cause for clearly-erroneous data points in the Met Office wind-profile messages being flagged as reliable.

NEW

DE also highlighted a few prolonged periods of bad data, which were associated with instrument problems. DAH, who took over the remainder of the MST radar report, subsequently explained the causes of these problems.

Although internal interference had been the predominant radar problem in recent years, only 4 instances have occurred during the past 6 months; on 26th and 27th February 2012, and on 8th and 14th June 2012. However, a new problem, which appears to be connected with the new beam steering components, has been seen with irritating frequency over the past few months. When a transmitter goes out of action, either through automatically shutting down or (less-commonly) through blowing its fuse or choke, the noise level is raised by several dB. This leads to a loss of several kilometres in altitude coverage for the st-mode observations and a reduced ability to detect echoes for the m-mode observations. However, the problem does not appear to otherwise degrade the quality of the data which remain. Instances of this problem have occurred on the following dates: 25th January 2012; 5th, 8th, and 17th February 2012; 2nd, 12th, 16th, and 17th March 2012; 2nd, 16th, 17th, 19th, 26th, 27th, and 30th April 2012; 7th, 11th, 17th, 18th, 19th, and 22nd May 2012; 4th, 6th, and 8th June 2012.

Sometimes it would be a few days before LD visited the site and restarted the offending transmitter. For

example, when LD was on holiday, a transmitter remained out of action 2nd - 11th April 2012. However, LD also made a large number of unscheduled visits to the site and thereby limited the amount of time affected by the problem. DAH thanked him for his dedication to this. LD and DAH initially relied on the raised noise level in the m-mode plots to estimate the time at which a transmitter had gone out of action. However, a beam steering controller software upgrade, applied by ATRAD on 11th April 2012, featured an improved e-mail alert system. Since the transmitter problem on 17th April 2012, DAH has known immediately which transmitter was affected and the exact time at which it went out of action.

LD has made a number of attempts to investigate the problem. It had primarily affected the transmitter powering antenna sector A. Consequently, on 10th February 2012, LD swapped over the transmitters powering sectors A and B. The fact that the problem now primarily affects the transmitter which had originally powered sector B demonstrates that it is sector A which is the primary source of the problem. On 15th May 2012 LD swapped over the cables connecting the phase lock unit to the transmitters for sectors A and B. Although it was not immediately obvious, this caused an instability which resulted in the diagnostic parameter "secondary radial chain exists" being active over a large part of the st-mode observations. The cables were reverted to their original positions on 17th May 2012.

Two transmitters were out of action on Friday 16th March 2012. LD visited the site on the following day (a Saturday). He replaced the fuse on TX3 but couldn't restart TX5, which was indicating a high voltage problem. He disconnected the corresponding receiver feed, to avoid the noise level becoming elevated. LD returned to site on Sunday 17th March and found 3 transmitters out of action. He did not manage to restart TX5 until 23rd March 2012, when he managed to trace the fault to the 6 kV power supply. He got the transmitter started again after he changed the bridge rectifier.

The signal processing software contains a known bug, which only becomes apparent following a break in the external internet connection that lasts for more than 24 hours. The time-continuity algorithm should only consider observations which occur within half an hour to either side of the dwell being quality-controlled. However, a break in internet connection somehow affects the data flow. This appears to cause the time-continuity algorithm to additionally consider the observations made within the relevant time interval on previous days. If the wind field changes only slowly, as it did after the loss of internet connection on 5th February 2012 (see section 3b), the problem may not be immediately apparent. DAH only became aware of the problem on 9th February, when he noticed that the radial data files were 1/10th of their normal size. Useful st-mode altitude cover had become noticeably reduced since the latter part of the previous day. DAH solved the problem by manually flushing the files through the system. Following the loss of internet connection on Sunday 19th February 2012, DAH cleared the problem first thing on the following morning. There is a clear gap in useful upper-tropospheric data 04:30 - 08:45 UT on the 20th. This will be filled when the data are reprocessed. No problems were seen in association with the loss of broadband on 16th March, 30th March, and 27th May 2012. This is probably because the modem was restarted within 24 hours in each of these cases.

In connection with action item 48.4.2, i.e. to investigate opportunities for returning the spare MST radar transmitter to working order, DAH is in the process of arranging for Chilbolton engineers to visit the site. Moreover, LD had contacted Tony Olewicz, the site technician until March 2009, to find out what he knew about the transmitter. This is what Tony had to say: *"The transformer on spare TX was manufactured to operate on UK 50 Hz mains. The original transformers were designed for American 60 Hz. That's why new one is bigger. It was a very tight fit and I was reluctant to run it for long periods. Then there was a big lightning strike [December 1999?] and I used spares from that TX to get the other 3 TXs running. There is a fault with controller board and fault with interface board - both originating from other TXs. The ICs [integrated circuits] that showed positive faults using IC tester were replaced on both boards. Others I could not check at Capel Dewi. The extractor fan was another (minor) problem. The feed-through [capacitors?] supplying mains to extractor fan may need replacing as they tend to ark to chassis"*. DAH suggested that it might be more-effective to rely on the availability

of currently-manufactured transmitters than to support one which is over 20 years old. GV, noting the current problems with the transmitter powering antenna sector A, warned that this issue still needed to be taken seriously.

DAH reported that the first Mesosphere Summer Echoes (MSEs) of the current season were seen, albeit briefly, on 22nd May 2012. As of 00:00 UT on 1st June 2012, m-mode observations are being made using 3 beam pointing directions. This was first introduced on 24th June 2011 and used until 00:00 UT on 1st August 2011. For the rest of the time, when mesospheric echoes are rarely seen, only a single vertical beam observation is made once per cycle. More will be said about MSEs in section 6d.

Finally, DAH reported that he had investigated the potential of the MST Radar to observe Low Earth Orbit (LEO) space objects for a poster presented at the MST13 workshop. This builds on actual observations of LEO objects made by the 3 GHz radar at Chilbolton. The transit time of LEO objects through the MST radar beam will be of the order of 1 s. Consequently the signals are unlikely to be easily-identifiable in a spectrum that represents observations collected over a period of 21 s. For this reason it will be necessary to modify the radar control software to allow pre-processed (i.e. coherently-integrated over 1/12th s) receiver samples to be saved. At present these samples are discarded after they have been used to derive Doppler power spectra. DAH had calculated the observation geometry for a particular orbit of the International Space Station (ISS) on 14th March 2012. It passed close to the centre of the SW12.0 beam at an altitude of 391 km. This would have caused it to be range aliased 4 times over, down to an apparent altitude of 15 km.

5. Guest Instrument Report

5a) FGAM instruments - GV

The boundary-layer wind-profiler (BLWP) has returned to Cardington. Quick-look data plots are available through the DIAMET website: <http://ncasweb.leeds.ac.uk/diamet/windprofile/>. JP asked GAP if he could create a link from the Cardington dataset webpage on the BADC to the FGAM wind-profiler page.

ACTION ITEM 49.5.1 GAP to create a link from the Cardington dataset webpage on the BADC to the FGAM wind-profiler page.

NEW

The Elight Lidar will return to RAL, around 7th July 2012, in connection with the Clearflo campaign. DPW will remain there until he is satisfied that the instrument is working properly. GAP asked GV if he again wanted access to images from the webcams that show sky conditions at the RAL site - which he did.

ACTION ITEM 49.5.2 GAP to provide GV with access to images from the webcams that show sky conditions at the RAL site for the duration of the Clearflo campaign.

NEW

The radiosonde equipment at the radar site will be used in connection with the forthcoming phase of the TROSIAD campaign during the latter part of July 2012.

5b) University of Manchester instruments - GV

The static lidar has not been used much since the end of 2011. It will be operated in support of the forthcoming phase of the TROSIAD campaign.

5c) Met Office GPS receiver

DAH read out a report from Jon Jones (JJ), who was not at the meeting.

JJ visited the radar site in May 2012 and discovered that there is a conflict between the PC and GPS receiver clocks. He hasn't seen such a problem before and thinks that he will need to replace the PC. Although he intends to do this, it is currently low on his list of priorities. Whilst JJ was in Aberystwyth, he visited Dr Eleri Pryse at Aberystwyth University to discuss the possibility of her using the the GPS data for ionospheric monitoring.

Data from 200+ sites are still being processed and assimilated operationally into the Met Office's European model. Data from JJ's global processing system are now being assimilated operationally into the Met Office's global model. He is now also processing data on a sub-hourly basis. This is a major advancement as the data are retrieved in real-time data streams, written to 15 minute raw data files, and processed every 15 minutes. This means the data are available with a minimum delay of 5 - 10 minutes. The data are being assimilated by Sue Ballard for testing in the UKV (i.e. 1.5 km horizontal resolution) southern UK model. Data from the global network are being processed to extract Total Electron Content (TEC) for Space Weather applications.

JJ has been nominated as Chair for a new GPS-centred COST Action which is focused on 3 main areas: real-time processing for nowcasting applications, advanced GNSS (Global Navigation Satellite System) processing (slants, tomography etc), and climate modelling. A pre-proposal, which was submitted in March 2012, has successfully passed the first phase of evaluation. A full proposal must be submitted by the end of July 2012. JJ is also now a member of the GRUAN (GCOS Reference Upper-Air Network) GNSS-PW (Precipitable Water) Task Team, which is concerned with the use of GNSS water vapour for climate applications. Water vapour is a GRUAN priority 1 observation.

5d) Lightning detector - DAH

This instrument continues to operate without the need for any attention.

6. Science and technical presentations

6a) A five-year radar-based climatology of tropopause folds and deep convection over Wales - BA
MST radar data have been used to identify tropopause folds that occurred during the period 2005 - 2010. The folds are characterised by enhanced values of wind shear and of signal power. Their occurrence is biased towards the winter months and is increased during positive phases of the North Atlantic Oscillation (NAO).

The second part of the analysis has involved looking at convective events that occur within a 100 km sided box centred on the MST radar site. Nimrod rainfall radar data must show a minimum value of 27 dBZ for 30 minutes in order for the event to be counted. The climatology shows a minimum rate of occurrence during the period February - April. There are two maxima: one in July and a second in November. DE commented that the distribution looked like that for lightning occurrence. Summer events tend to be within isolated cells, whereas winter ones tend to be part of organised systems. BA has also investigated the thermodynamic annual cycle by examining data from Aberporth radiosondes. The two diagnostics he has used are the mean water vapour mixing ratio over the lowest 100 hPa of the atmosphere and the mean lapse rate over the interval 700 - 500 hPa. Summer convection tends to be driven by the humidity term whereas winter convection shows more dependence on the mean lapse rate term.

The final part of the analysis involves a combination of the two climatologies. This reveals where convection is preferentially found in relation to tropopause folds. There are fewer isolated cells on the eastern side of the fold compared to the western side. Moreover, the Convective Available Potential Energy (CAPE) tends to be increased on the eastern side, indicating more-organised conditions. BA speculated that the orography of Wales plays a role in the patterns seen. GV advised that he would need to examine case studies in order to demonstrate this.

GV confirmed that the standard MST radar observation format, which was used for the late-2011 DI-AMET/TROSIAD campaign, should be used for the forthcoming campaign phase in late July 2012.

6b) Atmospheric Dynamics Research Infrastructure in Europe (ARISE)- CFL

CFL has recently started a post-doc position in Reading and is working on the EU-funded ARISE project. Its aim is to design a new infrastructure for providing a 3D image of the atmosphere between the ground and the mesosphere. At present, lidar is the only technique for accurately measuring temperature at altitudes of above 40 km; satellite measurements have significant biases. MF and meteor radar measurements don't start until around 80 km. Airglow measurements can also be used at the higher altitudes. MST radars are not officially considered for the network. However, CFL thought that since they gave measurements for the stratosphere, it would be remiss to ignore them.

The focus of CFL's work will be on infra-sound, i.e. pressure variations ranging from 20 Hz down to the acoustic cut-off frequency (which is close to the Brunt-Väisälä frequency). An international detector network was developed for the purpose of supporting the Comprehensive Nuclear Test Ban Treaty. Stations are spread across the globe and are typically no more than 3000 - 4000 km apart. The propagation of infrasound is determined both by variations in the speed of sound, which depends on temperature, and by the wind vector. Reflections occur where the local speed of sound exceeds the value at the source region, e.g. from the upper-stratosphere and lower-thermosphere. It is possible for the infra-sound to be reflected multiple times between the atmosphere and the ground on its journey from its source to a detector. The propagation patterns are asymmetric owing to the predominant wind directions.

The aim of this work is to retrieve information about the atmospheric state from the detected infra-sound. Researchers at the Dutch meteorological service, KNMI, have had some success using ray-tracing techniques. Attention is focused on loud and known sources, e.g. the explosion at the Buncefield oil storage terminal in 2005, explosions at munitions dumps, and volcanic eruptions.

6c) Wind profiler (WP) impact measured by Forecast Sensitivity to Observation (FSO) tool - CG

The FSO tool allows measurements to be made of the change in forecast error associated with a particular observation. It is highly versatile and allows observations to be partitioned e.g. by their type or by model level. The forecast error is given by the total energy normalised by comparing the forecast at a particular time with the analysis.

CG gave an introduction to the maths behind this tool. She has assessed the impact of data from all WPs for the period August-September 2010 (GV warned that this period was dominated by high pressure over the UK and so the observations have an inherently low impact). There is a positive impact for Europe as a whole. There were difficulties with the WP at Payerne in Switzerland. This might be something to do with the complicated orography. There is a larger impact for WPs in Japan. The ageing US network shows only a marginal impact, although CG thinks that this might be a misrepresentation.

The Aberporth and Watnall radiosonde sites show a slight negative impact, although the error bars are larger than the offsets. CG wondered whether the availability of AMDAR data from aircraft lessened the impact of these sites. Other radiosonde sites show positive impacts. The Aberystwyth radar now shows a positive impact. The South Uist radar has a larger positive impact, particularly in the Low Mode. The impact of each WP profile is less than that of each radiosonde profile. However, if it is appropriate to add the impact of each individual profile over the course of a day (this has been done in several studies), the vastly-greater number of WP profiles will make them more significant than the (typically) two radiosonde profiles per day. Similar results are found for the German WPs, although the impact of individual WP and radiosonde profiles are more-similar to begin with at Lindenberg.

6d) Making sense of mesospheric echoes - DAH

Having accumulated 7 years' worth of continuous mesospheric radar observations (i.e. a single vertical beam dwell once every 5 minutes), DAH has finally begun to analyse the data in earnest. He presented a poster for the MST13 workshop, which compared the occurrence of Mesosphere Summer Echoes (MSEs) and of Noctilucent Clouds (NLCs) as a function of mesopause temperature. MSEs are known to rely on the existence of ice crystals, albeit of a smaller size than those which make up NLCs. The NLC observations were made by John Rowlands, an amateur observer based in Anglesey, i.e. approximately 100 km to the north of the MST radar site. Mesopause temperatures were provided by Nick Mitchell and Kerry Day from the University of Bath's meteor radar at Erange in northern Sweden.

Despite the large meridional separation between the temperature and MSE/NLC observation sites, there is a reasonable anti-correlation between NLC occurrence and mesopause temperature. This has already been attributed to influence of planetary waves, such as the 5 day wave, in modulating mesospheric temperatures. Such waves have large altitude and latitude extents and they propagate through all longitudes. However, the occurrence of MSEs is relatively-poorly correlated with that of NLCs and with mesopause temperatures. This might be because the existence of MSEs depends on the existence of suitable electron density structures (which are thought to be generated by turbulence) as well as on the existence of ice crystals. The frequency spectrum of MSE daily duration does, however, show a predominant periodicity of between 4 and 5 days. This work is now being extended to make use of mid-latitude temperature data from the MLS instrument on NASA's Aura satellite.

DAH has had to develop a simple mesospheric echo detection algorithm for this work. The reliability flagging used by the version 3 signal processing scheme was optimised for the st altitude region. It is not effective for the m-mode. The new algorithm is somewhat conservative but generates few false positives. This has allowed the differences in characteristics between MSEs and non-summer mesospheric echoes to be established. DAH drew attention to a set of extraordinarily-extensive echo layers observed on 31st January 2012. These looked much more like MSEs than non-summer echoes. Moreover, one of the layers did not appear until after 19:00 UT. The lack of sunlight should have precluded the existence of free electrons, which are necessary for radar returns to occur. DAH speculated that geomagnetic effects, associated with the enhanced solar activity at around this time, may have played a role.

DAH pointed out that there is a small uncertainty as to the interpretation of m-mode range gate numbers. A programmable read-only (PROM) memory chip automatically blanks the altitude region between the top of the st-mode and the bottom of the m-mode. There is evidence in legacy computer code that some uncertainty existed as to the first range gate in the m-mode. However, this was compounded by changes made to the new data acquisition system introduced in February 2007 - http://mst.nerc.ac.uk/announce_20080416.html. GV warned that this issue would need to be resolved before this work could be published.

7. Any Other Business

GV warned that NERC are being obliged to make large savings. Cuts to all funding streams, including that for the MSTRF, should be expected.

The next Experimenters' meeting, to be held at the Cosener's House, was provisionally scheduled for Thursday 24th January 2013.